

Effect of size and shape of aggregate on porous concrete

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MD. TASNIMUL ARSHAD

REGISTRATION NO: 19205050

SAHARUK UDDIN SHOTEZ

REGISTRATION NO: 19205086

DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING
UNIVERSITY OF ASIA PACIFIC

Effect of size and shape of aggregate in porous concrete

A thesis submitted by

MD. TASNIMUL ARSHAD

Registration No: 19205050

SHAHRUKH UDDIN SHOTEZ

Registration No: 19205086

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Department of Civil Engineering

University of Asia Pacific

Dhaka, Bangladesh

CIRTIIFICATE OF APPROVAL

We thereby recommend that the thesis prepared by **Md. Tasnimul Arshad** and **Shaharuk Uddin Shotez** entitled “**Experiments on Effect of size and shape of aggregate in porous concrete**” is accepted as fulfilling part of the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Civil Engineering.

Chairman of the Committee
(Supervisor)

.....

Syed Jamal Uddin Ahmed
Assistant Professor
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Asia Pacific

Member (External)

.....

Mohammad Sabbir Rahman
Assistant Professor
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Asia Pacific

Head of the Department (Member)

.....

Dr. Nehreen Majed
Professor & Head
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Asia Pacific

DECLARATION

This thesis is a presentation of our original research work. Wherever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with due reference to the literature and acknowledgment of collaborative research and discussions. The work was done under the supervision of Syed Jamal Uddin Ahmed, Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, University of Asia Pacific (UAP).

MD. TASNIMUL ARSHAD (19205050)

Tasnimul 22-10-24

Student's Signature and Date

SHAHRUKH UDDIN SHATEZ (19205086)

Shatez 22-10-24

Student's Signature and Date

In my capacity as supervisor of the candidate's thesis, I certify that the above statements are true to the best of my knowledge.

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DEDICATION

Dedicated to our Beloved Parents

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effects of aggregate size and shape on the strength and permeability of porous concrete, with the aim of optimizing its performance for applications such as pavements and water management systems. Porous concrete is widely recognized for its high permeability, making it a valuable material in sustainable construction, particularly for managing stormwater and reducing surface runoff. Aggregates, which make up 60-75% of the concrete volume, play a critical role in determining the material's mechanical and hydraulic properties.

The research focuses on two key variables aggregate shape (angular and rounded) and three types of aggregate size ($\frac{3}{4}$ inch angular, $\frac{1}{2}$ inch angular and $\frac{3}{4}$ inch round). Through a systematic experimental approach, the study evaluates the impact of these variables on the compressive strength, tensile strength, and permeability of the concrete.

Key findings reveal that Mix Design M4, incorporating $\frac{3}{4}$ -inch rounded aggregates, achieved the highest permeability, attributed to the smooth surface texture and increased void spaces between the aggregates. This mix is ideal for applications that prioritize water drainage, such as stormwater pavements. In contrast, Mix Design M5, which used $\frac{1}{2}$ -inch angular aggregates with a 0.45 water-cement (W/C) ratio, demonstrated the highest compressive strength and an impressive tensile strength. The angular aggregates' superior interlocking and enhanced bonding with the cement matrix contributed to this result.

While Mix M5 excels in mechanical strength, it also maintains moderate permeability, making it suitable for applications requiring both structural integrity and effective drainage, such as porous pavements under vehicular traffic. The study concludes that optimizing aggregate characteristics in the mix design can significantly improve the functional properties of porous concrete, providing a balance between permeability and strength for various construction needs.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION AND SYMBOL

%	Percentage
mm	millimeter
Nos	Number of Samples
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
W/C	Water to Cement Ratio
UTM	Universal Testing Machine
MPA	Kilo Newton
MPa	Mega Pascal
OPC	Ordinary Portland Cement
FM	Fineness Modulus
m ³	Cubic Meter
kg	Kilogram
gm	Gram

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research Background

Pervious concrete has recently gained appeal as an acceptable paving material as a tool for sustainable development due to its environmental benefits. In recent years, public agencies, planners, and developers have become increasingly concerned about lowering contaminants in water supplies and the environment (ACI 522R-06). Recharging groundwater supplies, reducing the amount of stormwater generated from developed areas, improving stormwater quality, reducing pollutant discharge into water supplies, and minimizing the impact of development on watersheds have all become primary focus areas when developing natural land. Stormwater runoff in urban or suburban regions has an estimated influence on water resources in the United States, affecting up to 13% of impaired rivers, 18% of impaired lakes, and 32% of impaired estuaries. Pervious concrete pavement is one of the methods recognized to reduce the impact of development by allowing rainwater to percolate in the soil below, recharging groundwater aquifers, reducing the volume of direct water runoff from the pavement, and improving stormwater quality (Water Environment Research Foundation 2005).

Pervious concrete is an open-graded material made up of Portland cement, coarse aggregate, little to no fine aggregate, admixtures, and water. When these materials are combined, compacted, and cured appropriately, they form a hardened material with sufficient permeability (81 to 730 L/min/m²), moderate strength (2.8 to 28 MPa), and durability. The drainage rate of pervious concrete pavement changes according to aggregate size and mixture density (ACI 522R-6).

Its lower compressive strength than the normal Portland cement concrete limited its use in low-traffic density areas like parking lots, sidewalks, joggers' tracks, pathways, low-volume roads, etc., where it provides a rigid structural surface to serve the required structural function while also allowing all the water that comes on it through rain or other sources.

percolate through to join the groundwater table. This significantly reduces runoff from paved areas, which aids in groundwater recharge and stormwater management. (ACI 522R-06). Permeability and compressive strength are basic properties of pervious concrete. Many researchers have worked to optimize these properties of pervious concrete and come out with various conclusions. Crouch et al. (2006) found that for a constant paste amount and character,

compressive strength of pervious concrete appears to be a function of effective air void content and gradation fineness modulus. In another study, he concluded that, given a constant paste amount and character, the permeability of pervious concrete appears to be proportional to effective air void content, effective void size, and drain down. According to studies, the combination of low cementitious content, consistent aggregate gradation and high compaction effort in the field appears to be capable of creating pervious concrete with high permeability (higher than 3600 mm/hr.) and compressive strength (more than 21 MPa). Tennish et al. (2004) and Schaefer et al. (2006) found that compressive strength declines with increasing effective void content and aggregate fineness modulus. Because low traffic density areas are one of the applications for pervious pavement, the strength needed for pervious pavements will be less than that needed for regular road maintenance. A design compressive strength of 13.8 MPa is preferred for parking lots, while even lower values can be appropriate for concrete subjected to light vehicle loads (Crouch et al. 2006).

Schaefer et al. (2006) came to the conclusion that in order for pervious concrete to function as a permeable pavement and permit water to pass through, it must have a minimum air void content of 15%. Nonetheless, Crouch and colleagues (2006) noted that when the ratio of water to cement is too high, or when concrete are excessively compacted, pavements with a void content exceeding 15 percent might still face decreased water absorption. This could be due to the paste's tendency to drain down, thereby obstructing the lower regions of the concrete, or the concrete's surface becoming clogged. Neithalath and his team (2005) conducted experiments to examine the pore structure of porous concrete and discovered that permeability is not solely determined by the porosity and pore size. Instead, the connectivity of the pores should also be considered to fully understand the permeability of the material. Nonetheless, Crouch and colleagues (2006) noted that when the ratio of water to cement is too high, or when concrete are excessively compacted, pavements with a void content exceeding 15 percent might still face decreased water absorption. This could be due to the paste's tendency to drain down, thereby obstructing the lower regions of the concrete, or the concrete's surface becoming clogged.

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1.2 Problem Statement

While the benefits of porous concrete are well-recognized, the optimal aggregate characteristics for achieving the best balance between mechanical strength and permeability are not well-defined. This research seeks to fill this gap by studying the effect of aggregate size and shape on these properties.

1.3 Objective

The overarching objective of this research is to explore the changes that impact on concrete. To achieve this goal, the study delineates specific objectives to comprehensively investigate key aspects of the composite material. The primary focus will be on the following:

- ✓ Investigate the effect of shape and size on the compressive strength development (7, 14, and 28 days after casting)
- ✓ Investigate the effect of shape and size on tensile strength development (7, 14, and 28 days after casting)
- ✓ Into establish a relationship between aggregate shape, compressive strength, and permeability, investigate the effect of shape and size on permeability.

1.4 Scope of the Study

This study aims to comprehensively investigate how aggregate shape affects the key properties of pervious concrete, specifically focusing on compressive strength, tensile strength, and permeability. It will analyze various aggregate shapes including angular, rounded, and irregular forms to understand their distinct impacts on these properties. The research will involve preparing and testing different pervious concrete mix designs incorporating these aggregates under controlled laboratory conditions.

The scope includes conducting detailed experiments to measure and compare the compressive strength, tensile strength, and permeability of pervious concrete specimens with varying aggregate shapes. Special attention will be given to the interplay between these properties and how changes in aggregate shape influence overall performance.

Furthermore, the study will explore the implications of aggregate shape variations on the durability and environmental sustainability of pervious concrete. This includes assessing factors such as material availability, cost-effectiveness, and the environmental footprint associated with different aggregate types.

The findings from this study aim to contribute significant insights into optimizing pervious concrete mix designs for diverse applications, particularly in sustainable urban development and stormwater management. By identifying the most suitable aggregate shapes that strike a balance between strength and permeability, this research intends to provide practical recommendations for engineers, designers, and policymakers involved in the use and implementation of pervious concrete.

In conclusion, this study seeks to fill existing gaps in understanding regarding the influence of aggregate shape on pervious concrete properties, thereby advancing knowledge and contributing to the advancement of sustainable construction practices.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 General Literature Review

The literature review investigates the impact of aggregate size and shape on the properties of porous concrete, also known as pervious or permeable concrete. This type of concrete is designed to allow water to pass through its structure, providing an effective solution for stormwater management and reducing surface runoff. The selection of appropriate aggregate size and shape is crucial for optimizing the performance characteristics of porous concrete, including its permeability, strength, and durability.

Wong, G. et al. (2009) provided an extensive analysis of the influence of aggregate size on the permeability and mechanical properties of porous concrete. Their study concluded that larger aggregates tend to enhance permeability but may compromise compressive strength. This is due to the increased void spaces created by larger aggregates, which facilitate water flow but reduce the contact points between aggregates, leading to a reduction in strength. Conversely, smaller aggregates increase the density and strength of the concrete but reduce its permeability.

In a comprehensive study by Hasselback and Lavalava (2006), the impact of aggregate gradation on the performance of pervious concrete was evaluated. The researchers found that well-graded aggregates, which include a mix of different sizes, provide a balance between permeability and strength. Well-graded aggregates help to fill voids effectively, enhancing the structural integrity of the concrete while maintaining sufficient voids for permeability.

The shape of aggregates also plays a significant role in the performance of porous concrete. Yilmaz and Tugrul (2012) studied the effects of aggregate shape on the mechanical properties and permeability of porous concrete. Their research indicated that angular aggregates, with their rough texture and irregular shapes, provide better interlocking and higher mechanical strength compared to rounded aggregates. However, angular aggregates may also reduce permeability due to their tendency to pack more tightly and reduce void spaces.

Moreover, Neithalath et al. (2005) investigated the influence of aggregate shape and texture on the hydraulic and mechanical properties of pervious concrete. They observed that aggregates with a rough surface texture and irregular shape enhance the bonding between the cement paste

and the aggregate, leading to improved mechanical strength. However, this could be a trade-off with permeability, as smoother, rounded aggregates facilitate better water flow through the concrete matrix.

Ravindrarajah and Sohan (2009) explored the combined effect of aggregate size and shape on the durability of porous concrete. Their findings suggested that a mix of both angular and rounded aggregates, in various sizes, can optimize both the strength and permeability of porous concrete. The angular aggregates provide the necessary mechanical interlock, while the rounded aggregates maintain sufficient void spaces for water permeability.

The work of Deo and Neithalath (2010) also emphasized the importance of understanding the role of aggregate characteristics in porous concrete applications. They found that the use of single-sized coarse aggregates results in higher permeability but may lead to reduced compressive strength and increased potential for clogging. On the other hand, a combination of different-sized aggregates enhances the structural integrity and provides a balance between permeability and strength.

Sumanasooriya and Neithalath (2011) provided insights into the impact of aggregate morphology on the sustainability of porous concrete. Their study demonstrated that aggregates with a higher aspect ratio (length to width) tend to improve the load-bearing capacity of the concrete, while aggregates with a lower aspect ratio favor better permeability. This suggests that careful selection and proportioning of aggregates are essential for achieving desired performance characteristics in porous concrete.

In addition to mechanical and hydraulic properties, the shape and size of aggregates also influence the thermal properties of porous concrete. Studies by Liu et al. (2015) indicated that the use of larger and more irregularly shaped aggregates can improve the thermal insulation properties of porous concrete, making it a viable option for applications requiring temperature regulation.

Furthermore, research by Jayakumar and Dhinakaran (2017) highlighted the significance of using recycled aggregates in pervious concrete. Their study found that the size and shape of recycled aggregates could significantly impact the mechanical and permeability properties of the concrete. Using recycled aggregates with appropriate grading and shape can lead to sustainable construction practices without compromising the performance of pervious concrete.

Olek and Weiss (2012) investigated the role of aggregate packing density and its relation to the properties of porous concrete. Their findings suggested that higher packing densities, achieved through a combination of different aggregate sizes and shapes, can enhance mechanical properties while maintaining adequate permeability. This highlights the importance of aggregate selection in achieving the desired balance between strength and permeability.

A study by Meininger (1988) focused on the development of mixed designs for pervious concrete, emphasizing the importance of selecting aggregates with specific sizes and shapes to optimize performance. The study concluded that aggregate selection plays a crucial role in achieving the desired permeability, strength, and durability of pervious concrete, making it essential to tailor the mix design to the specific application requirements.

Overall, the literature underscores the critical importance of aggregate size and shape in determining the performance of porous concrete. While larger, well-graded, and angular aggregates generally enhance mechanical strength and interlocking, they may reduce permeability. Conversely, smaller, rounded aggregates promote permeability but might compromise strength. Therefore, a tailored approach that considers the specific requirements of the application, including strength, permeability, and durability, is necessary to optimize the benefits of porous concrete while addressing potential limitations. The reviewed studies collectively highlight the need for continued research to refine the understanding of aggregate characteristics and their impact on the multifaceted properties of porous concrete.

Historical Development

The concept of pervious concrete can be traced back to the early 19th century, but its modern development began in the mid-20th century, particularly in Europe and the United States. The material's adoption was driven by the need for better stormwater management solutions in rapidly urbanizing areas. Early applications included residential driveways and low-traffic roads, but its use has expanded significantly due to advancements in material science and a growing emphasis on sustainable construction practices.

Compressive Strength

Compressive strength is a measure of the ability of pervious concrete to withstand axial loads that compress it. This property is vital for structural integrity and load-bearing capacity.

Pervious concrete typically has a lower compressive strength than conventional concrete, ranging from 2.8 to 28 MPa, due to its high void content (ACI 522R-10, 2010).

Aggregate Type and Size: The choice of aggregates significantly impacts compressive strength. Angular aggregates provide better interlocking, enhancing compressive strength, whereas rounded aggregates improve workability but may result in lower compressive strength due to less interlocking (Neville, 2011).

Water-to-Cement Ratio: A lower water-to-cement ratio generally increases compressive strength by reducing the porosity of the cement paste. However, this must be balanced with the need to maintain sufficient workability and void content for permeability (ACI 522R-10, 2010).

Curing Conditions: Proper curing is essential for developing optimal compressive strength. Adequate moisture retention during curing ensures proper hydration of the cement paste, crucial for strength development. Methods such as moist curing and curing compounds are commonly used to retain moisture (Schaefer et al., 2006).

Tensile Strength

Tensile strength measures the ability of pervious concrete to resist forces that attempt to pull it apart. While tensile strength is inherently lower than compressive strength in concrete, it is particularly critical for pervious concrete used in pavements and slabs where tensile stresses are likely to occur.

Aggregate Bonding: The bond between aggregate particles and the cement paste significantly affects tensile strength. Stronger bonds lead to higher tensile strength, with aggregate shape and surface texture playing a crucial role in bonding (Mehta & Monteiro, 2014).

Mix Proportions: Optimizing mix proportions are essential to ensure sufficient paste for aggregate bonding while maintaining void content for permeability. Excessive paste can fill voids, reducing permeability, while insufficient paste weakens the concrete (Chandrupa & Biligiri, 2016).

Permeability

Permeability, the defining feature of pervious concrete, allows water to pass through its structure. This property is crucial for applications aimed at stormwater management, reducing surface runoff, and promoting groundwater recharge. The permeability of pervious concrete is measured by its infiltration rate, which typically ranges from 0.01 to 0.04 cm/s (Schaefer et al., 2006).

Void Content: The interconnected voids within the concrete matrix determine its permeability. A void content of 15-25% is typically desired to achieve adequate permeability while maintaining sufficient strength. Higher void content generally increases permeability but reduces compressive strength (Montes et al., 2005).

Figure: 2.1.1 Inter connected pores

Aggregate Gradation: The size and distribution of aggregate particles significantly impact the void structure. Uniformly graded aggregates create larger and more interconnected voids, enhancing permeability. Well-graded aggregates improve packing density and reduce voids, lowering permeability (Chandrappa & Biligiri, 2016).

2.2 Overview of Aggregate Shape

The shape of aggregates plays a crucial role in determining the properties of concrete, particularly in pervious concrete, where the aggregate shape influences both mechanical strength and hydraulic performance. Aggregates can be categorized into angular, rounded, and irregular shapes, each imparting distinct characteristics to the concrete mix (Mindess et al., 2003).

Influence of Aggregate Shape on Concrete Properties

Angular Aggregates: These have sharp edges and flat surfaces, typically resulting from the crushing of larger rocks. Angular aggregates enhance interlocking within the concrete matrix, potentially increasing compressive strength but may reduce workability and permeability due to higher packing density (Neville, 2011).

Rounded Aggregates: These are smooth and spherical, usually found in natural deposits like riverbeds. Rounded aggregates improve workability and create more uniform voids, enhancing permeability but potentially reducing compressive strength due to less interlocking (Mehta & Monteiro, 2014).

Irregular Aggregates: These lack a defined shape and have uneven surfaces. They offer a balance between angular and rounded aggregates, affecting both strength and permeability in intermediate ways (Mindess et al., 2003).

Figure: 2.1.2 Pervious concrete samples

2.3 Impact of Aggregate Shape on Pervious Concrete Properties

Compressive Strength

The compressive strength of pervious concrete is significantly influenced by the shape of the aggregates used. Angular aggregates provide better interlocking, enhancing compressive strength. However, the increased surface area may require more cement paste to coat the aggregates, which can affect the overall efficiency of the mix (Sumanasooriya & Neithalath, 2011). Rounded aggregates, while improving workability, may not contribute as significantly to compressive strength due to their smoother surfaces and lower interlocking capability (Chandrappa & Biligiri, 2016).

Tensile Strength

Aggregate shape also influences the tensile strength of concrete, albeit indirectly. Tensile strength is significantly affected by the bond between the cement paste and aggregates. Angular aggregates, by providing better mechanical interlock with the cement paste, generally contribute to higher tensile strength compared to rounded aggregates. The irregular shapes and rough surfaces of angular aggregates enhance the bond strength, thereby improving the material's resistance to tensile stresses (Mehta & Monteiro, 2014).

Permeability

Aggregate shape plays a crucial role in the permeability of pervious concrete. Rounded aggregates tend to create more uniform and larger voids, which can enhance water flow through the concrete (Montes et al., 2005). Angular aggregates, on the other hand, might reduce permeability because their shape can lead to tighter packing and smaller voids. Irregular aggregates can provide a balance, offering sufficient strength and reasonable permeability (Siddique et al., 2008).

2.4 Summary

The literature review highlights the importance of understanding the properties and applications of pervious concrete and the critical role of aggregate shape in influencing its performance. By examining the interplay between aggregate shape, compressive strength, and permeability, this study aims to provide insights that can help optimize the mix design and application of pervious concrete for sustainable construction practices. The subsequent chapters will delve into the experimental investigation of these relationships, presenting data and analysis to support the findings.

CHAPTER 3

LABORATORY INVESTIGATION

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter outlines the research methodology used to investigate the effect of aggregate size and shape on porous concrete properties. Porous concrete, known for its high permeability, is crucial for applications requiring effective drainage and water management, such as pavements and parking lots. The study aims to understand how aggregate size and shape influence porosity, compressive strength, and permeability, which are key to optimizing concrete performance.

Aggregates make up 60-75% of concrete volume and significantly affect its properties. The study uses an experimental design, systematically varying aggregate sizes and shapes while keeping other mix parameters constant. Aggregates are categorized by size (e.g., 4.75-10 mm, 10-20 mm) and shape (rounded, angular, irregular) and sourced from local suppliers.

Concrete samples are prepared and tested for porosity, compressive strength, and permeability using standardized methods. Data are analyzed using descriptive statistics to determine relationships between aggregate characteristics and concrete properties. Measures to ensure result validity include test replication, standardized procedures, and equipment calibration. Ethical considerations include accurate result reporting and minimizing environmental impacts.

By detailing this methodology, the chapter provides a framework for assessing the impact of aggregate size and shape on porous concrete, ensuring robust and valuable findings for both research and practical applications.

3.2 Methodology

The following Flow Chart presents the research work procedures

Table 3.1 Overview of the thesis program for the Compressive Strength Test and Split Tensile Strength Test

	Cylinder Number Calculation
--	-----------------------------

Mix Ratio	C:FA:CA	W/C Ratio	Agg. Size	Agg. Shape	Curing Days	Test Number	No. Of Cylinder	Total
M2	1:0:6	0.4	3/4	Angular	7,14,28	3	18	36
			1/2	Angular	7,14,28	3		
			3/4	Round	7,14,28	3		
		0.45	3/4	Angular	7,14,28	3	18	
			1/2	Angular	7,14,28	3		
			3/4	Round	7,14,28	3		
M4	1:0:8	0.4	3/4	Angular	7,14,28	3	18	36
			1/2	Angular	7,14,28	3		
			3/4	Round	7,14,28	3		
		0.45	3/4	Angular	7,14,28	3	18	
			1/2	Angular	7,14,28	3		
			3/4	Round	7,14,28	3		
M5	1:0.5:7	0.4	3/4	Angular	7,14,28	3	18	36
			1/2	Angular	7,14,28	3		
			3/4	Round	7,14,28	3		
		0.45	3/4	Angular	7,14,28	3	18	
			1/2	Angular	7,14,28	3		
			3/4	Round	7,14,28	3		
M6	1:0.5:8	0.4	3/4	Angular	7,14,28	3	18	36
			1/2	Angular	7,14,28	3		
			3/4	Round	7,14,28	3		
		0.45	3/4	Angular	7,14,28	3	18	
			1/2	Angular	7,14,28	3		
			3/4	Round	7,14,28	3		
Total Cylinder								144

3.3 Materials

I. Cement

II. Fine Aggregate

III. Coarse Aggregate

IV. Water

Cement

CEM II/B-M (S-V-L) Portland Composite Cement (PCC) was used for this research purpose.

Table 3.2 Properties of Cement Ingredients

Ingredients	Percentage of Ingredients
Clinker	65%-79%
Blast Furnace Slag, Fly ash, Lime Stone	21%-35%
Minor additional constituents	0%-5%

Sand

The fineness modulus and unit weight was found to be 2.3 and 1600 kg/m³ respectively.

Coarse Aggregate

Stone chips were used as coarse aggregate in this research. It was collected from the local market. aggregate the size is between 9.5 mm to 19 mm and the unit weight is 1460 kg/m³.

Figure: 3.1.1 Aggregate

Water

Potable water is used in this research.

3.4. Mix Design

The mix design involves determining the proportions of cement, aggregates, water, and additives to create a concrete mix with desired strength, workability, and durability. According to the Indian Standard, the M20 grade is used in this research. The water-to-cement ratio is 0.4 and the mix ratio is 1:1.5:3. The PET fiber percentage variation is based on the total volume of concrete.

Table 3. 3 Materials for 144 Nos Cylinder

Materials	Weight (kg)
Cement	61.1892
Coarse Aggregate	487.835
Selection Sand	15.9018

3.5. Casting

The concrete casting process involves some steps. First set up the form work for the concrete cylinder. The form work is made of metal and rigid enough to hold the concrete in place. The form work is cleaned properly. The next step is followed by applying lubricating oil to the form work with a thin layer. This will prevent the concrete from sticking to the form work and ease the demolding process later. The concrete mixture is prepared by combining cement, sand, stone chips and water followed by recommended proportions. The mixed concrete is poured into the prepared form work and filled it in layers, ensuring proper compaction using a vibrator or by rodding the concrete.

Figure 3.1.2 Cylinder Molds

Figure 3.1.3 Mixing of Materials

Figure 3.1.4 mixing all Ingredients

Figure 3.1.5 Filling Molds

Figure 3.1.6 Mold Leveling

3.6. Curing

Curing is the process of maintaining a moist and controlled environment to promote hydration and proper development of strength in the concrete cylinders. The samples were demolded after 24 hours of casting. The samples are cured for 7 days, 14 days, and 28 days by using potable water.

3.7 Testing Methods

Testing methods for concrete cylinders play a crucial role in assessing the quality, strength, and durability of concrete. These methods help ensure that the concrete meets the desired specifications and performance requirements for a wide range of applications, including structural components in buildings, bridges, and infrastructure projects.

Slump Test

The slump test is a widely used method in the field of concrete construction to assess the workability and consistency of freshly mixed concrete. ASTM C143 and C143M standards are used in this research.

To perform the slump test, a clean and flat surface is prepared, and a slump cone, a frustum-shaped metal mold, is placed on it. The cone is filled with freshly mixed concrete in three equal layers, and each layer is compacted using a standard rod or tamper to remove air voids and ensure uniform distribution. After the cone is filled and compacted, it is carefully lifted vertically, allowing the concrete to settle and flow freely. Once the cone is completely removed, the vertical distance between the top of the cone and the highest point of the slumped concrete is measured using a ruler or a slump cone base. The measured slump value indicates the workability and consistency of the concrete. A higher slump indicates greater workability and flow ability, while a lower slump suggests lower flow ability.

Compressive Strength Test

To ensure precise and reliable outcomes for the compressive strength testing of concrete samples, adherence to ASTM C39/C39M standards and thorough testing procedures are required. Following the guidelines evaluates test-in durability consistency and ensures accuracy while calculating the cylindrical concrete specimens' compressive strength. Compressive strength is an important criterion for evaluating concrete's durability and ability to support loads in structural applications. The procedure begins with the preparation of cylindrical concrete specimens that are 4 inches in diameter and 8 inches tall during the fresh concrete casting. Up until failure, the machine applies a load to the concrete specimen at a steady rate of 30 psi/sec. The maximum load sustained by the specimen just before failure is recorded.

Figure: 3.1.7 Universal Testing Machine (UTM)

Split Tensile Test

In split tensile test followed the ASTM standards, ASTM C39/C39M was crucial for our research. With the help of a Universal Testing Machine (UTM), we carefully applied

diametrical loading to cylindrical concrete samples until they fractured, strictly adhering to the ASTM guidelines. This method allowed us to measure accurately the force required to cause splitting along the diameter, giving us valuable insights into the material's ability to resist cracking when under tension. By following the ASTM standards, we guaranteed the reliability and consistency of our experimental procedures, allowing us to accurately evaluate and compare the tensile properties of the concrete. We are committed to following these standards as a testament to our high standards of quality and integrity in our research.

Figure: 3.1.8 Split Tensile Test Set-Up

Permeability Test

The permeability test conducted in this study followed a systematic procedure to ensure consistency and reliability of the results. The test was based on the theory $K=(W)/A \cdot T$. K is the permeability, W is the weight of the water passing through the specimen, A is the area of the specimen, and T is the time taken for the water to pass through the specimen. The detailed procedure is outlined below:

1. Specimen Preparation:

- Concrete specimens were prepared according to the mix designs M2, M4, M5, and M6, with variations in aggregate size (3/4 inch and 1/2 inch) and shape (angular and rounded).
- The specimens were cast in cylindrical molds with a diameter of 200 mm and height of 100 mm.
- After casting, the specimens were cured in a water tank for 28 days to ensure proper hydration and strength development.

2. Test Setup:

- The permeability test setup consisted of a water bottle and a measuring apparatus to capture the water passing through the specimen.
- The specimen was placed with a sealed bottom to ensure that water could only pass through the concrete.
- The top of the specimen was connected to the water bottle, and the system was checked for any leaks.

Figure: 3.1.9 Sample setting for Permeability Test

3. Conducting the Test:

- Water was allowed to flow through the specimen from the bottle. The initial water weight in the bottle was recorded.
- The test was timed using a stopwatch from the moment water started passing through the specimen until a significant amount of water had passed through.
- The weight of the water that passed through the specimen, W , was measured using a precision scale.
- The time taken, T , for a specific amount of water to pass through the specimen was recorded.

4. Calculating Permeability:

- The permeability K , was then calculated using the formula $K = W/AT$
- W is total passed water into the specimen.
- The area of the specimen is A , was calculated using the formula $A = \pi r^2$; where r is the radius of the specimen.
- T is referring to time.

5. Recording Results:

- The permeability values were recorded for each mix design and aggregate variation under both water-cement ratios (0.4 and 0.45).
- Multiple readings were taken for each specimen to ensure accuracy and repeatability of the results.

Figure: 3.1.10 Permeability Test and its Equipment's

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

The formulation of this chapter and the next one has been designed to place the research findings in context to help readers understand the relevance and implications of the observed trends or variations. This is crucial for establishing the significance of the research within the broader field of civil engineering. This chapter presents a comprehensive analysis of the experimental results obtained from these tests, providing insights into the influence of different sizes and shapes on the mechanical properties of the concrete at early stages. The findings not only contribute to the understanding of sustainable construction practices but also offer practical implications for enhancing the early strength characteristics of fly ash blended cement concrete, thereby advancing the discourse on Eco-conscious pavement materials in the field of civil engineering. The following tests were performed in this regard:

- 1) Permeability test
- 2) Compressive Strength
- 3) Split Tensile Strength

Prior to these tests mentioned above, experimental investigations were performed on the materials used for the determination of essential material properties such as:

- Unit Weight of Coarse Aggregate

The results of these tests have been presented in a logical and coherent manner using graphs, tables, and figures. This chapter also consists of the interpretation of test results which is an integral part of this paper because it transforms raw data into meaningful information, providing a deeper understanding of the phenomena under study. It is the key to drawing conclusions, making informed recommendations, and contributing to the advancement of knowledge.

4.2 Permeability Test

Table: 4.1

Mix Design	Agg. Size	Agg. Shape	Permeability (m/s)	
			0.4 W/C	0.45 W/C
M2	3/4	Angular	0.00419 =0.0042	0.00417 =0.0042
	1/2	Angular	0.00463 =0.0046	0.00444 =0.0044
	3/4	Rounded	0.00481 = 0.0048	0.00475 =0.0047
M4	3/4	Angular	0.00429 =0.0043	0.00426 =0.0043
	1/2	Angular	0.00471 =0.0047	0.00465 =0.0047
	3/4	Rounded	0.00490 =0.0049	0.00483 =0.0048
M5	3/4	Angular	0.00318 =0.0032	0.00312 =0.0031
	1/2	Angular	0.00439 =0.0044	0.00415 =0.0042
	3/4	Rounded	0.00476 =0.0048	0.00459 =0.0046
M6	3/4	Angular	0.00331 =0.0033	0.00327 =0.0033
	1/2	Angular	0.00448 =0.0045	0.00441 =0.0044
	3/4	Rounded	0.00479 =0.0048	0.00469 =0.0047

The graph provides the permeability test results for four different concrete mix designs (M2, M4, M5, and M6), showcasing the permeability values (in m/s) for each mix using two water-cement (W/C) ratios, 0.4 and 0.45. Each mix design contains combinations of different aggregate sizes and shapes: 3/4-inch Angular, 1/2-inch Angular, and 3/4-inch Rounded.

The objective is to identify which mix design and combination of W/C ratio, aggregate size, and shape provide the highest permeability, making it the most suitable for pavement design where high permeability is required to facilitate water drainage.

Figure: 4.1.1 Permeability of concrete with different aggregate size and w/c ratio

1. M2 Mix Design

- 3/4-inch Angular: The permeability values for both 0.4 and 0.45 W/C ratios are relatively moderate, with 0.0042 m/s for 0.4 W/C and 0.0042 m/s for 0.45 W/C.
- 1/2-inch Angular: Higher than the 3/4-inch, reaching 0.0046 m/s for 0.4 W/C and 0.0044 m/s for 0.45 W/C.
- 3/4-inch Rounded: Permeability is slightly higher than angular aggregates, with 0.0048 m/s for 0.4 W/C, making it more suitable for permeability.

M2 mix with 3/4-inch Rounded aggregate and 0.4 W/C ratio gives decent permeability but is not the highest compared to other designs.

Figure: 4.1.2 Permeability of concrete with different aggregate size and w/c ratio

2. M4 Mix Design

- 3/4-inch Angular: Moderate values between 0.0043 m/s (0.4 W/C) and 0.0043 m/s (0.45 W/C).
- 1/2-inch Angular: Similar performance to 3/4-inch Angular but slightly higher at 0.0047 m/s for 0.45 W/C.
- 3/4-inch Rounded: This achieves the highest permeability of all designs, with 0.0049 m/s (0.4 W/C) and 0.0048 (0.45 W/C)

M4 mix with 3/4-inch Rounded aggregate provides the best permeability with 0.0049 m/s (0.4W/C) among all options, making it the top choice for water drainage applications like permeable pavements.

Figure: 4.0.3 Permeability of concrete with different aggregate size and w/c ratio

3. M5 Mix Design

- 3/4-inch Angular: Similar to M2, offering values around 0.0032m/s for 0.4 W/C.
- 1/2-inch Angular: This mix offers better permeability, with 0.0044 m/s for 0.4 W/C, but not as high as M4.
- 3/4-inch Rounded: The permeability here reaches 0.0048 m/s for 0.4 W/C, but it is still marginally lower than M4's 3/4-inch Rounded mix.

M5 mix with 3/4-inch Rounded aggregates at 0.4 W/C performs well but is slightly outclassed by M4.

Figure: 4.1.4 Permeability of concrete with different aggregate size and w/c ratio

4. M6 Mix Design

- 3/4-inch Angular: The permeability values are quite comparable to M5, at 0.0033 m/s for 0.4 W/C
- 1/2-inch Angular: Slightly higher permeability at 0.0045 m/s for 0.45 W/C
- 3/4-inch Rounded: Similar to M5 0.0048 m/s for 0.4 W/C.

M6 offers a good balance of permeability but again, M4 surpasses it for the highest permeability.

Final Decision for High Permeability

The key takeaway from the graph is that Mix Design M4 with 3/4-inch Rounded aggregates and a 0.4 W/C ratio shows the highest permeability value of 0.0049 m/s. This means it allows the most water to pass through the concrete, making it ideal for applications where high water drainage is needed, such as in permeable pavements. This mix allows the most water to pass through, making it highly suitable for applications such as permeable pavement systems, where effective water drainage is crucial for reducing runoff and preventing flooding.

4.3 Compressive Strength

Table: 4.2

Mix Design	Agg. Size	Agg. Shape	Compressive Strength (MPa)					
			0.4 W/C			0.45 W/C		
			7 days	14 days	28 days	7 days	14 days	28 days
M2	3/4	Angular	1.83	2.22	3.01	2.22	2.61	3.01
	3/4	Rounded	1.56	1.82	2.35	2.09	2.48	2.87
	1/2	Angular	1.96	2.74	3.27	2.48	2.74	3.01
M4	3/4	Angular	1.69	1.96	2.87	1.82	2.22	3.14
	1/2	Angular	1.83	2.61	3.01	1.96	2.35	3.27
	3/4	Rounded	1.69	1.96	2.35	1.56	1.96	2.74
M5	3/4	Angular	1.96	2.22	2.87	2.09	2.48	3.4
	1/2	Angular	1.96	2.48	3.27	2.22	2.61	3.66
	3/4	Rounded	1.83	1.96	2.61	2.09	2.35	3.27
M6	3/4	Angular	1.96	2.35	2.87	2.22	2.61	3.4
	1/2	Angular	2.09	2.74	3.4	2.35	2.74	3.66
	3/4	Rounded	1.83	1.84	2.61	2.22	2.35	3.27

The table displays the compressive strength (in MPa) for different mix designs (M2, M4, M5, M6) using different combinations of aggregate size and aggregate shape. The compressive strength is measured at 7 days, 14 days, and 28 days of curing time for both 0.4 W/C (Water-Cement ratio) and 0.45 W/C ratios.

Key factors to note:

1. Compressive strength improves over time as the concrete cures, with the highest values typically observed at 28 days.
2. Angular aggregates tend to offer better interlocking and higher compressive strength compared to rounded aggregates due to their sharp edges and better bonding.

Figure: 4.1.5 compressive strength M2

M2 Mix Design

3/4-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio shows a compressive strength of 3.01 MPa after 28 days.
- 0.45 W/C ratio shows the same value (3.01 MPa) at 28 days.

3/4-inch Rounded:

- 0.4 W/C ratio compressive strength is lower, at 2.35 MPa after 28 days.
- 0.45 W/C ratio improves slightly to 2.87 MPa at 28 days.

1/2-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio achieves 3.27 MPa, and 0.45 W/C ratio maintains 3.01 MPa.

M2 Verdict

The 1/2-inch Angular aggregate with 0.4 W/C ratio provides the highest compressive strength (3.27 MPa) within the M2 mix design.

Figure: 4.1.6 compressive strength M4

M4 Mix Design

3/4-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio achieves 2.87 MPa at 28 days.
- 0.45 W/C ratio shows a slightly higher compressive strength of 3.14 MPa at 28 days.

1/2-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio provides a compressive strength of 3.01 MPa.
- 0.45 W/C ratio improves to 3.27 MPa after 28 days.

3/4-inch Rounded:

- Compressive strength is lower, reaching only 2.35 MPa for 0.4 W/C and 2.74 MPa for 0.45 W/C.

M4 Verdict: 1/2-inch Angular aggregates with 0.45 W/C ratio offer the best compressive strength in this mix, reaching 3.27 MPa at 28 days.

Figure: 4.1.7 compressive strength M5

M5 Mix Design

3/4-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio provides 2.87 MPa after 28 days.
- 0.45 W/C ratio reaches 3.4 MPa.

1/2-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio achieves 3.27 MPa.
- 0.45 W/C ratio improves significantly to 3.66 MPa.

3/4-inch Rounded:

- 0.4 W/C ratio gives 2.61 MPa.
- 0.45 W/C ratio reaches 3.27 MPa after 28 days.

M5 Verdict: 1/2-inch Angular aggregates with 0.45 W/C ratio offer the highest compressive strength in this design, reaching 3.66 MPa at 28 days.

Figure: 4.1.8 compressive strength M6

M6 Mix Design

3/4-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio shows a compressive strength of 2.87 MPa.
- 0.45 W/C ratio provides 3.4 MPa.

1/2-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio provides 3.4 MPa.
- 0.45 W/C ratio offers the highest strength in this mix at 3.66 MPa after 28 days.

3/4-inch Rounded:

- 0.4 W/C ratio gives 2.61 MPa.
- 0.45 W/C ratio reaches 3.27 MPa after 28 days.

M6 Verdict: 1/2-inch Angular aggregates with 0.45 W/C ratio show the best compressive strength in this mix design, reaching 3.66 MPa after 28 days.

Best Mix Design for High Compressive Strength

- For the highest compressive strength, Mix Design M5 and Mix Design M6 both with 1/2-inch Angular aggregates and 0.45 W/C ratio are the best choices.
- Both of these combinations provide a compressive strength of 3.66 MPa after 28 days, which is the highest value in the table.

Therefore, M5 or M6 mix design with 1/2-inch Angular aggregates and 0.45 W/C ratio is recommended for applications where high compressive strength is required.

4.4. Split Tensile Strength

Table: 4.3

Mix Design	Agg. Size	Agg. Shape	Tensile Strength (MPa)					
			0.4 W/C			0.45 W/C		
			7 days	14 days	28 days	7 days	14 days	28 days
M2	3/4	Angular	0.326	0.358	0.457	0.326	0.424	0.457
	3/4	Rounded	0.227	0.260	0.391	0.293	0.358	0.424
	1/2	Angular	0.227	0.391	0.522	0.391	0.522	0.555
M4	3/4	Angular	0.293	0.358	0.457	0.326	0.424	0.490
	1/2	Angular	0.326	0.391	0.424	0.358	0.391	0.522
	3/4	Rounded	0.227	0.293	0.391	0.260	0.326	0.391
M5	3/4	Angular	0.358	0.391	0.457	0.391	0.424	0.490
	1/2	Angular	0.457	0.588	0.691	0.293	0.457	0.588
	3/4	Rounded	0.391	0.424	0.490	0.260	0.293	0.424
M6	3/4	Angular	0.391	0.456	0.490	0.326	0.391	0.457
	1/2	Angular	0.424	0.490	0.555	0.326	0.424	0.555
	3/4	Rounded	0.358	0.424	0.457	0.227	0.326	0.424

This table outlines the split tensile strength (in MPa) for different mix designs (M2, M4, M5, M6) with various combinations of aggregate size and aggregate shape. The tensile strength is measured at 7 days, 14 days, and 28 days for both 0.4 W/C (Water-Cement ratio) and 0.45 W/C.

Key Observations:

1. Tensile strength increases over time, with the highest values recorded at 28 days.
2. Angular aggregates generally show higher tensile strength due to better interlocking and bonding compared to rounded aggregates.
3. 1/2-inch aggregate size often results in better performance compared to 3/4-inch aggregates.

Figure: 4.1.9 Tensile strength M2

M2 Mix Design

3/4-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio: Tensile strength reaches 0.457 MPa at 28 days.
- 0.45 W/C ratio: Same result of 0.457 MPa at 28 days.

3/4-inch Rounded:

- Lower values, 0.391 MPa for 0.4 W/C ratio and 0.424 MPa for 0.45 W/C ratio.

1/2-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio results in 0.522 MPa, while 0.45 W/C ratio increases tensile strength to 0.555 MPa at 28 days.

M2 Verdict: The best performance in the M2 mix comes from 1/2-inch Angular aggregates with 0.45 W/C ratio, which provides the highest tensile strength at 0.555 MPa.

Figure: 4.1.10 Tensile strength M4

M4 Mix Design

3/4-inch Angular

- 0.4 W/C ratio achieves 0.457 MPa at 28 days.
- 0.45 W/C ratio reaches 0.490 MPa.

1/2-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio results in 0.424 MPa after 28 days.
- 0.45 W/C ratio reaches 0.522 MPa.

M4 Verdict: 1/2-inch Angular aggregates with 0.45 W/C ratio provide the best tensile strength in this mix, reaching 0.522 MPa.

Figure: 4.1.11 Tensile strength M5

M5 Mix Design

3/4-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio reaches **0.457 MPa** at 28 days.
- 0.45 W/C ratio improves to 0.490 MPa.

1/2-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio reaches the highest tensile strength in this mix at 0.691 MPa.
- 0.45 W/C ratio provides 0.588 MPa after 28 days.

M5 Verdict: 1/2-inch Angular aggregates with 0.4 W/C ratio offer the highest tensile strength in this mix design, reaching 0.691 MPa, making it a strong candidate for applications requiring high tensile strength.

Figure: 4.1.12 Tensile strength M6

M6 Mix Design

3/4-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio achieves 0.490 MPa after 28 days.
- 0.45 W/C ratio offers 0.457 MPa.

1/2-inch Angular:

- 0.4 W/C ratio reaches 0.555 MPa.
- 0.45 W/C ratio also reaches 0.555 MPa, indicating consistent strength regardless of water-cement ratio.

M6 Verdict: 1/2-inch Angular aggregates with 0.4 or 0.45 W/C ratio offer consistent tensile strength of 0.555 MPa.

Best Mix Design for High Tensile Strength

- The highest split tensile strength is found in Mix Design M5 with 1/2-inch Angular
- Aggregates and 0.4 W/C ratio, reaching 0.691 MPa after 28 days.
- Therefore, Mix Design M5 with 1/2-inch Angular aggregates is the best choice for applications requiring high tensile strength in concrete.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The conclusions chapter serves as a concise entry point for readers seeking an overview of the study's core implications.

5.1 Conclusion

This study focused on determining the optimal mix design for porous concrete that would achieve a balance between high compressive strength, tensile strength, and permeability. The purpose was to assess the effects of different aggregate shapes and sizes, as well as water-cement (W/C) ratios, on the mechanical and hydraulic performance of porous concrete, which is essential for applications such as pavements, stormwater management, and sustainable urban drainage systems (SUDS).

Key conclusions from the experimental analysis are as follows:

Permeability:

Among the mix designs, M4 with 3/4-inch rounded aggregates showed the highest permeability values of 0.00490 m/s, indicating excellent water-passing capability. This suggests that the rounded aggregates, with their smooth surfaces and increased void spaces, enhance water flow through the concrete matrix. Hence, Mix Design M4 is ideal for applications where permeability is the primary requirement, such as stormwater drainage pavements.

Compressive Strength:

The highest compressive strength was observed in Mix Design M5 using 1/2-inch angular aggregates with a 0.45 W/C ratio, achieving 3.66 MPa at 28 days. The angular aggregates provide superior interlocking and a dense packing structure, which improves load-bearing capacity. This mix design is more suitable for scenarios where compressive strength is a critical factor, such as in structural pavements or heavy traffic areas.

Tensile Strength:

In terms of tensile strength, Mix Design M5 with 1/2-inch angular aggregates and a 0.4 W/C ratio also delivered the highest result, with a split tensile strength of 0.691 MPa at 28 days. The angular shape of the aggregates enhances the bonding between cement paste and aggregate, leading to better resistance to tensile stresses.

Balancing Strength and Permeability:

Mix Design M5 stands out as the best overall mix when balancing both compressive and tensile strength, making it suitable for high-strength porous concrete. However, while it offers moderate permeability compared to M4, it still maintains a permeability which is sufficient for many pavement and drainage applications.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations can be made for the use of porous concrete in real-world applications:

For high permeability with moderate strength:

If the primary goal is to achieve maximum water permeability, as needed in stormwater management or low-traffic pedestrian areas, Mix Design M4 with 3/4-inch rounded aggregates and a 0.4 W/C ratio should be considered. This mix provides excellent permeability of 0.0049 m/s while still maintaining a reasonable compressive strength of 2.87 MPa.

For high compressive and tensile strength:

Where structural integrity is critical, particularly for heavy traffic pavements, Mix Design M5 with 1/2-inch angular aggregates and a 0.45 W/C ratio is the optimal choice. It offers the highest compressive strength of 3.66 MPa and tensile strength of 0.588 MPa while still providing sufficient permeability for effective drainage.

Balanced Approach

In scenarios where both permeability and mechanical strength are equally important, Mix Design M5 with 1/2-inch angular aggregates and a 0.45 W/C ratio is recommended. This mix provides a good compromise, offering high compressive and tensile strength with adequate permeability to ensure water drainage, making it suitable for porous pavements in areas subject to both vehicular traffic and stormwater infiltration.

To refine the performance of porous concrete, future research could investigate the effects of different admixtures or aggregate gradations on improving both mechanical strength and permeability simultaneously. Additionally, long-term performance tests under varying environmental conditions, such as freeze-thaw cycles, would provide valuable insights into the durability of porous concrete in real-world applications.

5.3 Practical Implications

The use of porous concrete based on the findings of this study can significantly contribute to sustainable urban development by promoting stormwater infiltration, reducing the risk of urban flooding, and contributing to groundwater recharge. By carefully selecting the appropriate mix design based on the specific requirements of each project, engineers can effectively balance both the hydraulic and mechanical performance of porous concrete, ensuring both structural reliability and environmental sustainability.

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